

Development of Jaw Script Recognition Media Through Card Media Using Augmented Reality For Elementary School Children

*¹Bagus Hirnov Baihaqi, ²Yusfia Hafid Aristyagama, ³Dwi Maryono

*¹Informatics and Computer Engineering Education Teacher Training and Education Faculty, Sebelas Maret University

^{2,3}Informatics and Computer Engineering Education Teacher Training and Education Faculty, Sebelas Maret University

Corresponding Email : Hirnovbaihaqi11@student.uns.ac.id

Abstract:

This research aims to develop and determine the feasibility of android learning media on the subject of Javanese script using augmented reality and card games for elementary school children. This research was conducted because of the lack of interest of students in learning Javanese script which is considered difficult and unimportant because it is less useful in terms of its usefulness in life practice and keeping Javanese script sustainable. The study used the ADDIE model with feasibility test stages using TAM. The result of the development of learning media is the creation of the "NGAKSARA" application as well as the "KARA" card media which can help students in introducing Javanese script. At the feasibility test stage, it was found that the learning media "NGAKSARA" is suitable for use in teaching and learning activities.

Keywords: *Android Applications, Augmented Reality, Javanese Script, Learning Media*

JGHTT (Journal of Global Hospitality and Tourism Technology)

Vol 1 Issue 1 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12590353](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12590353)

Received: 25/05/24 Revised: 25/05/24 Accepted: 26/05/24 Online: 29/06/24

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Introduction

Rese Indonesia is a country that has a variety of cultures, ethnic groups, religions, and beliefs. Culture itself is divided into various kinds, namely dance, songs, art, traditional clothing, languages, and so on. One of the cultures in Indonesia is the culture of Java. Javanese culture itself has its uniqueness such as community beliefs, language, arts, and traditions. Currently, Javanese culture, especially the Javanese language itself, is still used daily (Indah Puji Astuti et al., 2020). Javanese script is one of the Javanese cultures that are currently rarely used and even began to be replaced with Latin script. Therefore, the government made efforts to preserve the Javanese script by including the Javanese script in the educational curriculum (Kartikasari & Nugroho, 2010).

The condition of the Covid-19 pandemic has resulted in extraordinary changes, including in the world of education which is forced to transform suddenly from offline to *online*. Based on circular Letter Number 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of education policies during the emergency period of the spread of Corona Virus (Covid-19). Thus, education during the Covid-19 pandemic which requires students to study from home is considered to be able to reduce student interest in learning because in online learning students do not play an active role in learning (Kristina et al., 2020).

So far, teachers have more often used the lecture method where this method puts the teacher as the main element in learning without any accompanying media for teachers other than textbooks which cause the creation of two-way communication between students and teachers which results in quite a lot of students who are less skilled in writing Javanese letters less and the learning methods implemented lack variation. Until now, teachers still have difficulties in terms of introducing Javanese script. There are three aspects of elementary school students' learning, namely convenience, fun, and visualization. *Augmented Reality* can be applied in education because it has the advantage of being able to provide new experiences for users, especially elementary school students, as well as convenience, visual understanding, and fun so that students can attract children's attention (Ramadhan et al., 2021)

Based on Edgar Dale's cone theory, it is explained that by learning using stimulation and direct experience students can absorb material up to 90% (Cahyaningtyas, 2020).

Figure 1 Edgar Dale's Cone

Research Method

This research uses the ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) development model because this model is developed programmatically with systematic sequences of activities to solve learning problems related to learning resources that are following the needs and characteristics of students.

Figure 2 ADDIE Model

The ADDIE model has several stages starting with the analysis stage conducting interviews and reviewing the literature to identify problems, user characteristics, and determine the needs in developing learning media and become an initial reference in the development of learning media. The second stage of design at the stage is made a learning media design that will be made such as flowcharts, user interfaces, gameplay, and marker designs. The third stage of development of learning media is based on the analysis and design stage that has been made which then at

this stage is also carried out media validation and material validation. The fourth stage of the implementation of learning media has been made at the development stage to be tested on students to find out student acceptance of learning media and find out the feasibility of the learning media created. The fifth stage of evaluation is the stage of data processing obtained from the results of student respondents as well as validation from media experts and material experts with formulas which are then interpreted based on the following table:

$$\text{Persentase kelayakan}(\%) = \frac{\text{skor yang diobservasi}}{\text{skor yang diharapkan}} \times 100\%$$

Table 1. table interpretation (Ernawati, 2017).

Skala Presentase	Keterangan
0% - 20%	Tidak Layak
21% - 40%	Kurang Layak
41% - 60%	Cukup Layak
61% - 80%	Layak
81% - 100%	Sangat Layak

This research involved 1 lecturer as a media expert, 1 teacher as a material expert, and SDN students in the city of Surakarta as validators and also as respondents.

Result and Analyst

This study aims to develop Javanese script learning media using the ADDIE method and conduct feasibility tests or evaluations of learning media made using the Walker and Hess model that has been adjusted by (Arsyad, 2015) and TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) that have been adjusted (Mulyani & Kurniadi, 2015) whose results are described as follows:

Analysis Stage

At the analysis stage, problems were found when learning the subject of Javanese script teachers still use the lecture and book method which makes there is no two-way communication between students and teachers so many students are less skilled in reading and writing Javanese letters. Based on the above problems, a Javanese script learning media was developed using augmented reality and card games to help teachers and students learn Javanese script. The learning media that is made requires students to play in groups with three card play games so that students get direct experience in learning Javanese script which students hope can absorb 90% of Javanese script material based on Edgar Dale's cone theory.

Design Stage

At this stage, the design is carried out starting with flowcharts, markers, and gameplay Flowchart Design Flowchart as a reference for making learning media so that all activities in the learning media can be in line with what is designed.

Figure 3 Flowchart

Marker Design

The card marker design stage is a medium that will be scanned when the learning media is used. By giving some ornaments related to Javanese culture.

Figure 4 Marker Design
Play Game Design

At this stage, a gameplay design is carried out which aims to evoke emotional and intellectual responses from players as well as the occurrence of interactions between players and the games created and increase student learning motivation (Nugraha & Manggalastawa, 2021). When using learning media using cards consisting of three games as follows:

Game 1

The game can play with 2 to 4 players. Shake the cards and then position the cards closed and place them in the middle of the player. One player opens a card and then all players guess what the script of the opened card looks like in turn. After the player opens and guesses the card the player who opens the card performs a scan using the application to find out the shape of the open card script. The player who guessed correctly gets 10 points and to win the game the player must collect 100 points

Games 2

The game can play with 2 to 5 players. Once the player is collected and ready to play, shuffle the cards. One player acts as a word string that will string cards into a word. After the word stringing makes a word from the card another player guesses what script makes up the word. After finishing guessing the player who strings the word performs a scan using the application. Furthermore, the word string matches the scan results with the player's guesses. Players who manage to guess get 100 points for each word. To win the match the player must collect 500 points

Games 3

The game can play with 2 to 5 players. Once the player is collected and ready to play, shuffle the cards. One player acts as a word string using Javanese script. After the word stringing makes the word other players guess what script has been assembled using a card with the card position closed. After all, players have finished guessing the guessed card that was originally reversed, it is opened. Furthermore, the word maker scans the players' guesses. Players who manage to guess get 100 points for each word. To win the match the player must collect 500 points

Development Stage

The development stage starts with creating 3D objects in Javanese script using blender software.

Figure 5 creating 3d objects

Next, create background assets and learning media buttons.

Figure 6 background assets and buttons

Then create a scene on learning media consisting of the mainmenu scene, start, basic competencies, instructions, and developers

Figure 7 an example of creating a scene menu

After creating the scene, scripting is done to connect between scenes referring to flowcharts. Finally, a learning

media build was carried out to the android.

Table 2 application script

Script Name	Description
SceneManagement.cs	This program/script serves to manage the movement of scenes.
Backsound.cs	This program/script functions to adjust the audio backsound
BacksoundOff.cs	The program serves to turn off the backsound
CameraFocus.cs	This program/script functions to adjust the focus on the camera when scanning the marker
PlaySound.cs	This program serves to play the dubbing of the Javanese script that appears when the sacaning is performed
Initview.cs	The program adjusts the volume of the backsound

Figure 8 Build learning media

After the learning media application is built in android platform, testing is carried out using Blackbox testing. This test selects the purpose of knowing whether there is a wrong function or not according to the plan through two stages, namely functional test and non-functional test. Here's a look at the application scene and the results of the Blackbox test that has been carried out:

Table 3 Application Scene

Scene Name	Scene View	Information
Main Menu		The main menu is a start page that displays a menu or contains buttons that users can access when using learning media.
Begin		In this start menu, the main feature of the learning media application is to scan markers that will bring up 3D objects in the form of Javanese characters. In this feature, there are 2 buttons, namely playing sound and exiting.

Basic Competencies		On the basic competency menu, display the KI KD taken in this study
Instructions		In this menu displays instructions for using the application "NGAKSARA"
Developer		This menu displays a profile of the application developer "NGAKSARA"

Functional Testing

Table 4 functional testing results

No	Yard	Input	Process	Output	Result
1	Main Menu	Start button	Open the camera for a scan	Myproject Page	Appropriate
2		Basic Competencybutton	Opening the basiccompetency page	Komdas Page	Appropriate
3		Hint Button	Go to the instructions page	Instruction page	Appropriate
4		Developer Button	Opening the developer page	Developer page	Appropriate
5		Sound on/off button	Turn <i>background</i> on/off	<i>Background</i> on/off	Appropriate
6		Exit button	Display a "yes or no" info popup	Pop up info "yes orno"	Appropriate
7		Yes button on popups	Quit the app	Exit the app	Appropriate
8		The button is not onthe popup	Return to the main menu	Main menu page	Appropriate
9	Basic competencies	Menu button	Open the main menu page	Main menu page	Appropriate
10	Hints	Menu button	Open the main menu page	Main menu page	Appropriate
11	Developer	Menu button	Open the main menu page	Main menu page	Appropriate
12	Start	Sound play button	Play the sound of the script	Voice of the script	Appropriate
13		Exit button	Return to the main menu	Main page	Appropriate

Non-fungsional Testing

Table 5 results of non-functional testing

Device Name	OS version	Screen Size (pixels)	Testing	Result
Vivo Y83	Android 8	720 x 1520	Main Page	Successful

			Info Page	Successful
			Developer Page	Successful
			Instructions Page	Successful
			Scanning	Successful
			Main Page	Successful
Samsung GalaxyA20	Android 9	720 x 1520	Info Page	Successful
			Developer Page	Successful
			Instructions Page	Successful
			Scanning	Successful
			Main Page	Successful
Infinix Smart 5	Android 10	720 x 1600	Info Page	Successful
			Developer Page	Successful
			Instructions Page	Successful
			Scanning	Successful
			Main Page	Successful
Xiaomi Redmi 9	Android 11	1080 x 2340	Info Page	Successful
			Developer Page	Successful
			Instructions Page	Successful
			Scanning	Successful
			Main Page	Successful

Based on the results of the BlackBox test above, it was found that the results of the functional test of the learning media application could run as expected and the results of the non-functional test found at least the specifications of the smartphone, namely Android 8.

Then expert validation is carried out which is divided into 2, namely material experts and media experts. Expert validation itself adopts the adjusted Walker and Hess constructs (Arsyad, 2015).

Media Expert Validation

Validation of media experts is carried out by lecturers of the informatics engineering education study program, at Sebelas Maret University.

Table 6 media expert validation

No	Assessed aspects	Score
1	Clarity of instructions for the use of learning media	5
2	Level of flexibility in the use of learning media	5
3	Quality of material in learning media	5
4	Object Quality in learning media	4
5	Readability of letters in learning media (typeface)	5
6	Readability of letters in learning media (letter size)	5
7	Readability of letters in learning media (letter color)	5
8	The quality of background selection of learning media display	5
9	The quality of the use of color in learning media	5
10	Quality of display between pages in learning media	5
11	The size and quality of the objects displayed are appropriate	4
12	Object placement is appropriate	5
13	The displayed sound can be heard clearly	4
14	The design of the AR card is in accordance with the material presented	5
15	The quality of the opening display and the main menu of the learning media	5
Total Score		72

Based on the validation of media experts, the learning media application obtained a total score of 72 with a percentage of 96% so that it received a very decent predicate with a few expert comments as follows

Table 7 comments from media experts

No	Commentary
1	There is an error or BUG in the marker readings
2	Double and corresponding scripts or unreadable scripts do not disappear after the marker is not scanned

Material Expert Validation

The validation of material experts was carried out by one of the SDN teachers in the city of Surakarta.

Table 8 validation of material experts

No	Assessed aspects	Score
1	The material presented is in accordance with basic competencies	5
2	The material on the learning media is in accordance with the learning objectives	5
3	The material on the learning media is in accordance with the aspects taught	5
4	The material on the learning media is in accordance with the character of the students	5
5	The title conveyed by the media is in accordance with the material presented	5
6	The completeness of the material in the learning media is appropriate	5
7	The selection of content / content presented by the learning media is in accordance with the learning material	5
8	Selection of types of learning media according to user needs	5
9	The way the material is delivered to the media is in accordance with student development	5
10	Clarity of instructions for the use of learning media	5
11	Learning media has a positive impact on teachers in innovating learning activities	5
12	Learning media has a positive impact on the learning process	5
13	Quality of material in learning media	5
14	The quality of objects in learning media	5
15	Learning media is easy for teachers to use	5
Total Score		75

The results of the material expert validation found a score of 75 with a percentage of 100% so that the learning media application received a very decent predicate

Implementation Phase

The implementation phase was carried out on 22 grade 4 elementary school students in Surakarta. At this stage, students who have tested the application of learning media are given a questionnaire by adopting a TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) construct that has been adjusted by (Mulyani & Kurniadi, 2015) with a total of 20 questions divided into 3 research aspects, namely perceived usefulness perception 8 questions, perceived ease of use, 7 questions, and acceptance perception (Acceptance) 5 questions. The result of the obtained is as follows.

Table 9 User response

No	Assessed aspects	Score
Perception of Usefulness		
1	I find it helpful in understanding Javanese script using this application	3,7

2	I feel more active in learning Javanese script using this application	3,5
3	This application is useful in understanding Javanese script material	3,7
4	I feel that this application has a big impact on Javanese script learning activities	3,4
5	I feel that the quality of learning has improved thanks to this application.	3,6
6	This application makes it easier for me to learn Javanese script	3,7
7	This application makes it easier for me to learn Javanese script	3,5
8	This application suits my needs in learning Javanese script	3,3
Total score		28,4
No	Assessed aspects	Score
Perception of Ease		
1	This app is easy for me to use	3,3
2	The app is easy to use	3,7
3	The app is easy to understand	3,5
4	I can use this app without any written guide	3,3
5	I feel flexible in the use of the application	3,3
6	The application of Javanese script material to this application is easyfor me to learn	3,5
7	The addition of the displayed sound can be heard clearly	3,4
Total score		24
No	Assessed aspects	Score
Perception of Acceptance		
1	I am interested in using this application	3,5
2	I would suggest my friend use this app	3,4
3	I will often use this application to learn Javanese script	3,4
4	I will use this application regularly to learn Javanese script	3,4
5	I will use this application to increase my interest in learning Javanescript	3,5
Total score		17,2

The results of the user's response to the aspect of perceived usefulness obtained a score of 28.4 with a percentage of 71% and a decent predicate. The results for the perception aspect of ease obtained a score of 24 with a percentage of 68% and a decent predicate. The result of the perception of acceptance obtained a score of 17.2 with a percentage of 68% and a decent predicate.

Evaluation Phase

At this stage, an evaluation is carried out at the entire stage of assessing the feasibility of the application so that the final results are in accordance with the research objectives.

Evaluation of learning media

Evaluation of the feasibility of learning media is divided into three stages, namely material expert validation, media expert validation, and user response. Validation of media experts is carried out by informatics and computer engineering education lecturers using walker and hess assessment constructs. Producing a learning media application obtained a total score of 72 with a percentage of 96% so that it got a very decent predicate with a few comments and improvements made as follows:

Table 10 Improvements

No	Commentary	Repair
1	There is an error or BUG in the marker readings	Replacing the wrong marker design inthe readout

2	Double and corresponding scripts or unreadable scripts do not disappear after the marker is not scanned	Change the scan marker setting to only one marker so that there is no script buildup
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Expert validation of the material is carried out by primary school teachers using walker and hess assessment constructs. Producing a learning media application obtained a total score of 75 with a percentage of 100% so that it received a very decent predicate.

Assessment of user response feasibility using TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) construct is divided into 3 aspects of research with a total of 20 questions, namely perceived *usefulness* perception of 8 questions, perceived *ease of use*, 7 questions, and acceptance perception of 5 questions. The overall result of user response was a percentage of 68% with a decent predicate. The assessment was given because there are still some things that are felt to be lacking in terms of Javanese script objects that are incomplete also in the use of the "NGAKSARA" application, smartphones tend to heat up faster and the battery runs out faster.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The creation of the Javanese script learning media application "NGAKSARA" using the ADDIE development model which aims to be able to help students in introducing Javanese script as a learning medium and playing independently. The feasibility of the Javanese script learning media application "NGAKSARA" in the form of 3 assessments, namely the assessment or validation of media experts gets a very decent predicate, the validation of material experts gets a very decent predicate, and the results of the assessment of the response of users of the "NGAKSARA" application get a decent predicate. Based on the overall exposure, it can be concluded that the application of Javanese script learning media "NGAKSARA" is suitable for use in teaching and learning activities. This predicate is given because of the shortcomings seen by media experts, material experts and users

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